

Deliverable D9

Evidence of intended contributions to or influence on new or improved
international guides, recommendations and standards

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LiBforSecUse

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NPL

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25 February 2022 (M42)

1.2 IEC 63338: General guidance on reuse and repurposing of secondary cells and batteries

This document was developed by IEC SC 21A/PT 63338. NPL was represented on this working group by Dr Gareth Hinds, who contributed fully to the writing, commenting (through UK mirror committee BSI PEL 21), discussion and editing of the draft. The standard provides general guidance on the reuse and repurposing of rechargeable batteries (primarily Li-ion) for second life applications (see scope in Figure 2). The NPL contribution ensured that learnings from the testing and analysis tools developed under the LiBforSecUse project were fed into the testing and data specifications in Section 6: Considerations for Reused or Repurposed Battery Systems.

Figure 2: Opening page of CDV of IEC 63338 (Feb 2022).

2 Input to international standard test methods

While the general guidance and requirements standards described above are clearly important in the broader context of safe and reliable deployment of second life batteries, the test protocols developed during the LiBforSecUse project are more suited to incorporation in an international standard test method. Among the most commonly used and widely accepted international standard test methods for commercial Li-ion cells are the IEC 62660 series, which are summarised in Table 1. This is an obvious route for standardisation of the test protocols, as originally envisaged in the drafting of WP5 of the project.

Table 1: IEC 62660 series of standard test methods for Li-ion cells

Standard	Title
IEC 62660-1	Secondary lithium-ion cells for the propulsion of electric road vehicles - Part 1: Performance testing
IEC 62660-2	Secondary lithium-ion cells for the propulsion of electric road vehicles - Part 2: Reliability and abuse testing
IEC 62660-3	Secondary lithium-ion cells for the propulsion of electric road vehicles - Part 3: Safety requirements
IEC 62660-4	Secondary lithium-ion cells for the propulsion of electric road vehicles - Part 4: Candidate alternative test methods for the internal short circuit test of IEC 62660-3

At the final meeting of the LiBforSecUse project partners on 17 February 2022, a discussion was held on the most appropriate standardisation route for the project outputs. The main options were (i) to add the test method to an existing standard (e.g., IEC 62660-1) during its next scheduled revision or (ii) to create an entirely new standard.

It was agreed that the test protocols laid out in the Best Practice Guide would form the basis of a useful addition to the next scheduled revision of IEC 62660-1. This would be in the form of an Informative Annex. However, it was felt that further work on the data analysis component of the test methodology would be required before this could be incorporated in an international standard. For this reason, a staged approach to standardisation activities was unanimously agreed:

1. Addition of an Informative Annex in the next revision of IEC 62660-1, which will be coordinated by IEC TC21/JWG 69 Li in 2025. The Annex will contain a description of the impedance-based test protocols from the Best Practice Guide developed in the project. *(Action: NPL)*
2. When the data analysis component of the test method has progressed to the point at which it is ready for standardisation, a new work item will be submitted to IEC TC 21/JWG 69 Li. This could for example involve proposing a new part of IEC 62660 (e.g., IEC 62660-5), but consideration would be given at the time over whether it would be preferable to create a standalone standard. *(Action: NPL)*

In addition to the standardisation work through IEC, discussions with CEN/CENELEC are ongoing to assess whether some of the outputs of the project can be incorporated into new European standards on second life batteries, which are expected to be developed in the coming years. *(Action: NPL/PTB)*